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THE EMBODIMENT OF IDENTITY, SELF-SUFFICIENCY AND INDEPENDENCE IN THE NOVEL BY D. LESSING "THE GOLDEN NOTEBOOK"

Abstract

The work of D. Lessing, a prominent representative of modern English prose, is interesting in several respects. This is primarily notable for the fact that the writer destroyed the stereotypes existing in English prose and brought the latest trends of Western thinking to literature. Her prose is notable for its socio-political, anti-colonial, and communist views, as well as the artistic features of modernism and postmodernism. D. Lessing's novel "The Golden Notebook" contains problems that reflect the above-mentioned trends and keep the reader interested. The author of the article also tells the life story of an intellectual woman who fights for her identity, freedom, and puts independence above all else, and shows that the writer is far from the feminist label. The woman she describes does not fit into any mold, she is the embodiment of identity, self-sufficiency, and independence.

Keywords: *D. Lessing, "The Golden Notebook", Embodiment of Identity, Self-Sufficiency, Independence*

Introduction. The creativity of Dorris Lessing, a prominent representative of 20th-century English prose, Nobel Prize laureate, is often associated with feminist literature. The writer avoids this label and said to those who call her a "feminist writer" "The critics slap labels on you and then expect you to talk inside their terms" (Hazelton, 1982). According to D. Lessing, when you approach the issue ideologically, the world is divided into "bad" and "good". In the last periods of her creativity, she generally criticized radical feminism, calling it a new dogma that limits free thought. The writer was more interested in describing the world and man comprehensively, not maintaining any ideological framework, and not linking her personal views to rationalism or irrationalism: "I see inner space and outer space as reflections of each other. I don't see them as in opposition. Just as we are investigating subatomic particles and the outer limits of the planetary system - the large and the small simultaneously - so the inner and the outer are connected" (Hazelton, 1982). That is why she was upset when her novel "The Golden Notebook" (1962), which brought her world fame, was called a "feminist novel". D. Lessing, who did not consider herself a feminist writer, wrote that "What the feminists want of me is something they haven't examined because it comes from religion. They want me to bear witness. What they would really like me to say is, 'Ha, sisters, I stand with you side by side in your struggle toward the golden dawn where all those beastly men are no more.' Do they really want people to make oversimplified statements about men and women?" (Lessing, 2008).

But at the same time, the writer supported the women's liberation movement, recognizing their right to self-expression. Literary criticism, as a rule, divides Doris Lessing's early creativity into two periods. One of them covers the years 1949-1956 and is a period that combines socio-political, anti-colonial and communist views. This period includes the years when her books

"The Grass is Singing" and "Retreat to Innocence" were published. The second period of her early work mainly includes feminism, autobiographical works and especially psychological themes: "The Golden Notebook" and "The Children of Violence" that possesses the series of five novels are noted as significant events in her creativity.

Her works of mature period of creativity are distinguished by their tendency towards science fiction and Sufism. These include "Briefing for a Descent into Hell", "The Summer Before the Dark" and "Canopus in Argos" which consists of five novels.

Her recent period of creativity is mainly related to the reworking of the themes raised in the early period and the search for new creative ideas and themes: "The Diary of a Good Neighbour", "If the Old Could", "The Good Terrorist", "The Fifth Child", "Ben: in the World", "Playing the Game".

It should be noted that D. Lessing's novel "The Golden Notebook" is considered the pinnacle of the writer's creativity and among the works he has written so far, "it makes for a strange, troubling and difficult reading experience" (Jordison, 2019).

Main part. The novel "The Golden Notebook" is more about racial discrimination, communism, mental mindset and the concept of norms, and all these problems are described from the point of view of a woman. Anne Mulkeen writes that "for its unique and revealing portrayal of the twentieth-century's new woman" (Mulkeen, 1972). Therefore, it can be said that the problem of women is not dominant in the work, but harmoniously fits into the problems of modern man, becoming a translator of women. In other words, it talks about the rights and freedom of the individual in society.

The creation of the novel coincides with the years when feminist literary criticism was born. It was after this novel that feminist literature and the artistic understanding of its problems were widely studied.

During these years, the history of female writers who had equal rights with male writers was studied, the issue of women's self-expression in the art of the word, where patriarchal discourse existed, was taken into account, the accepted literary stereotypes were exposed by going beyond the traditional patriarchal literary canons, and the image of the subject-woman was restored in the text. The novel "The Golden Notebook" also reveals a new perspective in the narrative, going beyond the meaning of "female writer". Some attribute the novel's narrative to a postmodern style. Thus, a researcher studying the fictionality of a text puts forward the same idea: "fiction is an important technique in postmodernist novels" (Atamoglan, 2020). The heroine of the novel thinks about her position in society, highlights inequality in relations between women and men, shares her thoughts on love, creativity, and politics. In the preface to the work, the writer wrote that "she does not mean the women's liberation movement. She speaks of the anger and resentment of many women" (Lessing, 2008).

The novel consists of five parts, and between each part are notebooks reflecting the feelings and emotions of the heroine of the work, the talented writer Anna Wulf. The heroine writes her feelings in notebooks marked with four different colors, "escaping from chaos and formlessness, from helplessness, and trying to separate different objects". The past in Black Africa, red is dedicated to modern politics, yellow to literary creativity, and blue to everyday events. The author cuts Anna Wulf's notes in notebooks according to the reality that comes from the plot of the work, and it is interesting that each notebook ends with "two black lines." The fact that the heroine's notes in notebooks end meant that the novel does not end, because the colorful fragments create the fifth – "The Golden Notebook," and for Anna Wulf it meant getting out of the darkness, reaching clarity, finding the harmony of existence and creativity. The author writes in the preface: "In "The Golden Notebook", everything is united into a single whole, boundaries are erased, divisions are put to an end, and this was a triumph of thematic unity. Anna and Saul Greene destroy the artificial plot in which their pasts are located" (Lessing, 2008). Templates and forms are invented so that one can somehow create order and define oneself". They understand each other, recognize each other, and accept their thoughts in the last "Golden Notebook". For this reason, both write in the same notebook, but it isn't known whether it is Anna or Saul who writes. Saul gives Anna the topic for his new book, and Anna gives him her notebook, giving him the idea for work.

It is clear from the plot of the novel that the main character, depending on the circumstances, experiences serious nervous breakdowns, goes through a moral crisis, and reaches the point of going crazy. This moral crisis is a reaction to the environment surrounding her and the situation in society. The author brings the absurd and chaotic situation in the political and social environment in which an intelligent and sensitive woman lives to a peak. She tests her rational and emotional skills in various ways, bringing together a person's struggle for survival with moral values.

The novel's narrative describes the ideological innovations and conscious changes of Anna Wulf in the form of a story within a story. Anna Wulf's real crisis is written down by the real Anna Wulf in the last "The Notebook", and the reader sees the deep roots of the reasons that created the psychological state of the heroine. It is in the last notebook that the heroine regains her sense of self-confidence by gaining new strength, abandoning the idea of individual and social freedom and focusing not on personal freedom, but on the idea of change and renewal of society.

As can be seen, the author has created the image of a woman who has her own position in life and creativity, who can realize her own thoughts and point of view. For this, she pays attention to the psychology, internal state, identity of the heroine, and illuminates her gradual transition. In fact, D. Lessing, bypassing the problems of radical feminism, speaks only of women, talking about their equal existence as men. It is no coincidence that the heroine's surname is the same as that of Virginia Woolf, a member of the Bloomsbury group. It is known that Virginia Woolf paid special attention to the problems of creative women, writing about a strong woman who called herself a creative crisis. D. Lessing's heroine, Anna Wulf, is also able to get out of the crisis she falls into and resolve all conflicts harmoniously.

The work begins with the theme of conflict, and the heroine talks about the reality where "everything is falling apart, collapsing." Anna Wulf expresses her thoughts on the situation in certain circles of English society. This conflict situation is repeated many times throughout the work, gradually influencing the opening of other motifs and leitmotifs. The heroine believes that the reason for this is the fragmentary nature of society, the disappearance of interpersonal relationships, and the meaninglessness of life itself. Anna Wulf is a writer and writes the work "The Shadow of the Third". The absence of the principle of dialogue in interpersonal relationships, distrust are leitmotifs in the heroine's own life, in her diaries, in her novel, and in her four different colored notebooks. The heroine, who writes in her notebooks in different fonts, creates an atmosphere of dialogue with quotes cut from newspapers, sketches taken from literary works, and parodies. All this indicates the turmoil, suffering, and fragmentation in her inner world. As the work progresses, her inner suffering and psychological state deepen, and the heroine faces the threat of losing her identity. As if this were not enough, she falls into depression, lives with fear and anxiety.

From the beginning of the work, it becomes clear that Anna has been abandoned by the person she loves and she is suffering. This event is discussed from beginning to end with her friend Molly. Anna's novel "The Shadow of the Third" is built on the theme of separation. Anna's alter ego, Ella, the heroine of the novel "The Shadow of the Third", comes to the point of suicide after this event. However, the attentive reader sees that before reaching this point, the writer Anna goes to a psychologist at the very beginning of her relationship with her beloved Michael, complaining that she can't experience truly deep feelings. So, Anna,

who transfers herself to the image of Ella, was experiencing psychological shocks and was in search of her identity long before the work was written.

The turmoil in Anna's inner world was related to the events taking place in society, the country, and the world. She looked at events globally, experiencing every new crisis and disaster that occurred on a global scale. The tests with the atomic bomb, the polarization of the world, the division into good and evil, the numerous local conflicts that occurred in different parts of the world aroused in her a sense of regret, made her close herself. Anna first pasted newspaper materials in her notebook, and later on the walls of her apartment. The author presents her heroine as a socially responsible person who is sensitive to the pain of others, perceives the pain of others as her own and suffers because of this.

After Anna's psychologist examined her, it was decided that what was happening, the source of pain, should be sought not outside, but in her inner world. The reader can't understand the mental incompleteness of Anna, who gained world fame with her novel. What happens to her, a fairly well-off person, the mother of a successful child who lives as she wants and does not suffer from financial dependence, a person who is not left without attention from friends? Anna's endless suffering is connected with her individual worldview and attitude to world events. She can't be satisfied with herself, and can't easily relate to the suffering of those around her, she thinks that she is also morally guilty in what is happening. The disunity in society, the misunderstanding between people torment her. She thinks that she lives in a world where the bonds between people are severed. These thoughts, spoken by Ella, the heroine of Anna Wulf's novel "The Shadow of the Third", apply to Anna, she sees and describes the world in this way.

In order to restore her inner integrity, Anna decides that it is necessary to isolate her consciousness from some issues, to "close it off", to impose certain restrictions on herself. Repeated dreams of her mother frighten her, a "destructive nightmare" torments her. Evil force appears to her in various forms. First, it appears in the form of a dance of slanderous, bitter dishes, then in the form of a "cheerful old man" who destroys people, and finally in the form of a man she knows, and forces the heroine to come to this conclusion.

Dreams, fantasies, visions are observed with the awakening of the hero's personality. Along with the recurring nightmares of evil, Anna also sees good. These two events make her think, and she comes to the conclusion that destructive and good forces are combined in one person. When the two dancing dwarfs are understood as the fantasies hidden in Anna's individual creativity, the force that motivates her to the creative process, the hero finds comfort. The revelation of the secret of scary and incomprehensible dreams gives Anna real pleasure, prompting her to restore her creative potential. When conversations with the doctor come to her in a dream like a benevolent witch, she recognizes herself and comes to the conclusion that she can now help herself. The scene of crossing the Yellow

Sand Dune and climbing the mountain she saw in her dream once again proves to her that she is already at a new stage of life and will be able to overcome this heavy burden. It is interesting that in the scene of climbing the mountain in her dream, she sees an unfamiliar person. This person is her savior, her salvation. The psychologist explains that the person she sees is herself. In other words, it is her identity, her identity. That savior explains to Anna that she can fight with herself and win this battle. That is why it is necessary to return to the past, to "work" on it: "Every time I sit down to write, and let my mind go easy, the words, It is so dark, or something to do with darkness. Terror. The terror of this city. Fear of being alone" (Lessing, 2008: 46).

Throughout the work, it becomes clear that Anna's thoughts draw the line of her life, turning into a nightmare in a way that she does not want, but at the same time bringing her back to life. The thoughts that Anna records in her "Black Notebook" talk about the world and the wars it creates. People's thirst for death, their conscious approach to it, terrifies Anna: "Every time one of them arrives I want to laugh-the laughter of disgust. Bad laughter, the laughter of helplessness, a self-punishment. Unreal letters, when I think of a slope of hot pored granite, my cheeks against hot rock, the red light on my eyelids. Lunch with the agent. Unreal-the novel is more and more a sort of creature with its own life" (Lessing, 2008: 48). Anna struggles with her feelings, views these feelings as immoral. These immoral feelings cause her shame and regret. Anna protests, and her protest results in not writing a novel. The famous novelist expresses her protest in this way and therefore keeps notebook entries that only she can read.

Anna, who forbids herself from being creative, turns herself into an object of criticism in her notebooks rather than judging people and humanity. Anna judges only herself, not others. Anna does not expect anything like others, does not resent her loved ones, but on the contrary, gets along with everyone tries to go. Even when he criticizes someone inside, she blames herself, a sense of shame dominates her, she reproaches herself.

In the image of Anna, D. Lessing depicts a person who is caught between his personality and the laws of society, who is at war with her inner "I", who can't bring her creativity and reality together. Her creative personality, unlike an ordinary person, is immersed in fantasies in his dreams, subconsciously, and is driven to suicide in the reality she has invented: "The four notebooks were identical, about eighteen inches square, with shiny covers, like the texture of a cheap watered silk. But the colours distinguished them-black, red, yellow and blue. When the covers were laid back, exposing the four first pages, it seemed that order had not immediately imposed itself. In each, the first page or two showed broken scribblings and half- sentences. Then a title appeared, as if Anna had, almost automatically, divided herself into four, and then, from the nature of what she had written, named these divisions"(Lessing, 2008: 45).

"The Black Notebook" is a record of the peak of her fantasies, a step towards suicide. Here, death and

destruction, human disasters take place in shades of black. Notebook notes and newspaper clippings pasted on the wall reflect her inner world. In “The Blue Notebook,” the reader learns that Anna discussed with a psychologist not only the issue of not writing, but also the feeling of shame about what happened, and the affirmation of her own identity. “The Blue Notebook” is based on Anna’s rehabilitation, her gradual “coming to herself.” Anna moves away from self-judgment and enters the stage of self-acceptance, making peace with herself. However, in these notes, Anna still can’t regain her desire to write, and answers the question addressed to her “when will you write?” with: “Maybe never.” Anna’s creative sense is restored only in the notes of “The Golden Notebook,” and she finds herself as a writer when she begins to write together with her alter ego, Saul Green. As Karan Mahajan notes, “She dreams of generating “a new kind of strength” out of chaos, of wearing words like “insecure” and “unrooted” as a sort of badge” (Mahajan, 2020).

Conclusion. As a result of the four notebooks, Anna Wulf creates the fifth “Golden Notebook” by “bringing the four together” and in fact restores her identity, her inner integrity. The image of the Golden Notebook in this case becomes a characteristic feature of identity. It is in this notebook that Anna merges with the identity of Anna in the other four notebooks. Also,

as a creative person, she creates a whole androgynous creator in both feminine and masculine beginnings. The reader is fully convinced of this when he witnesses that the notes are taken by Saul Green along with Anna. For this reason, “The Golden Notebook” is the victory of Anna Wulf’s identity as a woman, a person, and a writer, a reflection of her personal integrity. D. Lessing also repeatedly disagreed with those who called “The Golden Notebook” a “feminist novel,” calling it the restoration of the integrity of the individual and the flagship of personal rights.

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